

ISic1576

I.Sicily inscription 1576

Language

Ancient Greek

Type

(?)

Material

tuff

(yellow)

Object**Editor**

Jonathan Prag

Principal Contributor

Jonathan Prag

Contributors

Jonathan Prag,James Cummings,James Chartrand,Valeria Vitale,Michael Metcalfe,Simona Stoyanova,Valentina Mignosa

Autopsy

No Autopsy

Last Change

2020-11-26 - Simona Stoyanova restructured bibliography

Place of origin (ancient)

Selinus

Place of origin (modern)

Selinunte

Provenance**Coordinates****Current Location**

Italy, Sicily, Palermo, Museo Archeologico
Regionale Antonino Salinas, inventory 8771

Physical Description

Dimensions

Height cm

Width cm

Depth cm

Layout

Execution

Engraved

Letter Forms

Letter heights:

Line 1: mm

Interlineation

Interlineation line 1 to 2: mm

Text

1. [---]NANIΘ[---]

2. [---] το ΑΙΔ[---]

Apparatus

Translation

Commentary

Digital identifiers:

TM 284879

EDR 112487

EDCS 41300086

PHI 175700

Bibliography

Manni Piraino, M.T. 1973. Iscrizioni greche lapidarie del Museo di Palermo.

Sikelika 6. Palermo. At 102

Manni Piraino, M.T. 1970. Epigrafia selinuntina. *Kokalos*. 16: 268-294. At 286
no.8

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